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**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>**Research****Article****PREVALENCE OF HYPERTENSION AMONG OUTDOOR
PATIENTS**Raisa Maryam¹, Saima Naz², Shahid Hussain³¹Dow Medical College Karachi²Fatima Jinnah Medical University³Basic Health Unit Murghai**Article Received:** November 2019 **Accepted:** December 2019 **Published:** January 2020**Abstract:**

Cardiovascular disease is a major health problem thought the world and a common cause of premature morbidity and mortality. In this cross-sectional study, a total of 150 outdoor patients presenting with symptoms of headache and irritability were included. All the data were entered and analyzed in SPSS Ver. 25.0. The mean age of the patients was 34.23 ± 2.34 years. There were 90 (60%) males and 60 (40%) females. The mean diastolic blood pressure of the patients was 85.23 ± 2.34 mmHg, The mean systolic blood pressure was 125.56 ± 1.90 mmHg. In patients presenting in outdoor, hypertension is more prevalent. So, education about suitable lifestyle modifications and prevention must be ensured.

Keywords: Outdoor, Hypertension.**Corresponding author:****Raisa Maryam,**

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INTRODUCTION:

Cardiovascular disease is a major health problem throughout the world and a common cause of premature morbidity and mortality. The burden of the chronic Non-Communicable Diseases (NCD), especially heart disease, stroke, hypertension, diabetes, cancer and chronic respiratory disease, is rising in the low and the middle-income countries, particularly in Asia. Hypertension is the most common disorder which is being encountered in the outdoor patients (1, 2).

It is an established major risk factor and a leading cause of cardiovascular diseases worldwide. Hypertension a silent killer is a major risk factor for cardiovascular disease worldwide and is one of the most important reasons to visit to physician. Hypertension leads to various complications as increased risk of stroke. The prevalence of hypertension and its complications are increasing in the developing countries. The economic development, changes in the lifestyle and diet, and an increase in the life expectancy may be attributed to this rapid increase (3, 4).

Hypertension is an established major risk factor and the leading cause of cardiovascular disease worldwide; the rate of hypertension and its complications are decreasing in developed countries whereas it is increasing in developing countries. Good control of blood pressure will result in prolonged survival. Increasing the knowledge,

awareness, and control of hypertension will reduce morbidity and mortality (5, 6).

Studies show that many patients did not have appropriate knowledge about hypertension. Hypertension is an iceberg disease. According to the studies, the percentages of the awareness, treatment, and the control of hypertension are unacceptably low in the Pakistani adult population (1, 5). In this study, we will see the prevalence of hypertension in outdoor patients.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

In this cross-sectional study, a total of 150 outdoor patients presenting with symptoms of headache and irritability were included. All the data were entered and analyzed in SPSS Ver. 25.0. The qualitative variables were presented as percentages and frequencies. The quantitative variables were presented as mean and standard deviation.

RESULTS:

The mean age of the patients was 34.23 ± 2.34 years, mean age of the male patients was 35.45 ± 2.56 years and of female patients was 33.46 ± 2.87 years. There were 90 (60%) males and 60 (40%) females. The mean diastolic blood pressure of the patients was 85.23 ± 2.34 mmHg, The mean systolic blood pressure was 125.56 ± 1.90 mmHg. Distribution of patients according to the systolic and diastolic blood pressure is given in the graph:

DISCUSSION:

It is of vital importance to have a good control of hypertension. Knowledge in our population is insufficient and partly associated with educational level, leaving much room for improvement by educational campaigns. As we know that undiagnosed, untreated, and uncontrolled hypertension clearly places a substantial strain on the health care delivery system and large benefits can be achieved by specially trained medical personals (4, 6).

The prevalence of hypertension ranged from 5-15% between 1960-1990. It had increased to 20-36% in the past decade. The factors which were attributable to this rising trend were the rapid urbanization, lifestyle changes, dietary changes and the increased life expectancy. The high prevalence of hypertension (44.46%) in the current study, confirmed this increasing trend. A compatible prevalence of hypertension was reported (46%) in a study which was conducted among the outdoor patients of an urban health centre of Kolkata (2, 5).

CONCLUSION:

In patients presenting in outdoor, hypertension is more prevalent. So, education about suitable lifestyle modifications and prevention must be ensured.

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